

Exceptional Summer Conditions and HABs of *Pseudochattonella* in Southern Chile Create Record Impacts on Salmon Farms

Fig. 1. Geographic distribution of *Pseudochattonella* sp. in the Inland Sea of the Xth Region (ISEX) during summer 2016.

The summer of 2016 was a great season for tourism in Southern Chile – however the fish farming industry was negatively impacted by exceptional harmful algal blooms of *Pseudochattonella* sp., along with minor blooms of *Alexandrium catenella* and *Leptocylindrus danicus*. This report focuses on the *Pseudochattonella* (= *Chattonella*) blooms at the Inland Sea of Region X in Chile (ISEX, Fig. 1). On 20th January 2016, phytoplankton samples were received at the Chiloé laboratory along with comments from a fish farmer, stating that Atlantic salmon had gill problems, low appetite and an increase in mortality rate. Results from the POAS (Programa Oceanográfico y Ambiental en Salmónidos) programme of Plancton Andino showed a mean of

64×10^3 cell L⁻¹ (CV 26 %) of *Pseudochattonella* sp. (Fig. 2) between 0 and 15 m in a relatively well mixed water column. Surface water temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen were 15.1 °C, 32.5 psu and 8.3 mg L⁻¹, respectively. This was not a typical mono-specific flagellate bloom for this time or place as *Pseudochattonella* sp. cells represented approximately 15 % of the total microphytoplankton community. The diatom *L. danicus* had an important ecological role afterwards (data not shown). The *Pseudochattonella* sp. bloom (maximum of 7.7×10^6 cells L⁻¹ on March 13) developed from the end of February to March 15th 2016, and resulted in massive fish kills in the

northern Chiloé Archipelago, Calbuco, and Reloncaví Sound and Fjord.

Blooms of *Pseudochattonella* sp were previously observed in the region, in 2004 ($\leq 4 \times 10^4$ cells L⁻¹) and 2009

Fig. 2. Light microscope images (x400) of different forms of *Pseudochattonella* sp.

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Fig. 3. Note the signal in late 2015 and 2016. Warm (+) and cold (-) periods based on a threshold of +/- 0.5°C for the ONI [SST anomalies in the Niño 3.4 region (5°N-5°S, 120°-170°W)]. Visit web page for details. ONI NOAA, Climate Prediction Center [4].

($\leq 4 \times 10^5$ cells L⁻¹), but from an economic point of view, this 2016 *Pseudochattonella* bloom has been the most damaging event in South America, with losses up to US \$ 500 M. The magnitude of the event was intensified by a climatic anomaly, among other features. This event, type of photoautotrophic flagellate, magnitude and economic impact is the first in Chilean HAB history [1-3].

El Niño and Meteorological Conditions: The recent “El Niño” signal in the South Eastern Pacific Ocean has been one of the strongest in the last decades [4]. Fig. 3 shows the inter-annual variability of the Oceanic Niño Index (ONI), with a large increase during the second semester of 2015. Additionally and as

consequence, the oceanographic and meteorological anomalies during summer 2016 in southern Chile have also been remarkable: Chile had one of the driest summers on record with a -70 % rainfall deficit until March 23th [5], with more solar radiation than normal, and positive sea surface temperature anomalies of 1-2 °C. Fig. 4 shows the Osorno Volcano, located close to the marine area under study on March 15, 2016. Lack of snow and increased ice melt on the upper part of the Osorno cone is unusual during the second half of the 20th century, but has been more common in recent decades.

Biological features of the bloom: During Summer 2016 the ISEX area

received warmer ocean waters and less freshwater influxes. Despite the lower run-off, thermohaline stratification developed (Fig. 5). It is known that autotrophic flagellates can be more competitive with high solar radiation, less wind stress and lack of upwelling. These flagellate cells can grow and/or aggregate in the pycnocline where density gradients are marked [6-8].

One of the main features of the event was its extremely high ichthyotoxicity, based on observations of extensive damage in salmon farms in a very short period of time (30 million fish killed in a few days). From an ecological point of view, the quasi-monoalgal thin layer formation of *Pseudochattonella* cells was the main feature. This feature was studied for more than 15 days. During the bloom, vertical CTD-O, *in situ* chlorophyll *a* and backscattering casts, and phytoplankton counts were made in the “hot spot” at the Seno Reloncaví area. We found surface temperatures above normal and sub-surface peaks of dissolved oxygen close to the 7-10 m layer. In most cases, phytoplankton assemblages and *in situ* vertical profiles of chl *a* fluorescence showed a sub-surface maximum in the pycnocline. This thin layer was dominated (93%) by *Pseudochattonella* cells (Fig. 6-7) which were photosynthetically very active ($F_o > 10$ and $F_m > 20$).

Fig. 4. Osorno Volcano, March 2016, showing the lack of snow and glacial melt at the upper part of the cone (Photo by Cristóbal Clément).

Fig. 5. Profiles of temperature, salinity, sigma-t and dissolved oxygen (mg/l) in Seno Reloncaví during the peak of the bloom (March 7, 2016).

Fig. 6. Vertical distribution of phytoplankton and *Pseudochattonella* (cell mL⁻¹), during the peak of the fish-killing event (March 7, 2016 at 1451).

Fig. 7. Vertical profile of in situ chl a (mg m⁻³) and backscattering ratio (470 nm/660 nm) of the thin layer of *Pseudochattonella* (same day and time as in Fig. 6).

Final Remarks: The southern Chile summer 2016 HABs and consequent massive salmon mortality reduced the actual and potential supply, creating a related increase in the international salmon price, and also variability in stock markets prices. Information from the fish farmers suggested that Coho Salmon is more resistant to this HAB than Atlantic salmon during this event. The climatic anomalies and thin layer formation, among other features, are key issues in the dynamic of the different stages of *Pseudochattonella* bloom at the ISEX area.

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Forthcoming: Guide to the Identification of Harmful Microalgae in the Gulf of Mexico

A manual entitled "*Guide to the Identification of Harmful Microalgae in the Gulf of Mexico*" is nearing completion and the English version will be available August 2016. The Guide has chapters on *Pseudo-nitzschia* and other diatoms (Meave and Zamudio), identification of dinoflagellates (Steidinger), and raphidophytes (Thomas) as well as chapters on methods for benthic dinoflagellate sampling (Tester and Kibler), dinoflagellate cyst sampling (Williams), water column sampling strategies (Christman and Steidinger), sample prepara-

tion and enumeration (Steidinger and Christman), the use of remote sensing in the study of HABs (Cannizzaro, Soto, and Hu). Also included are several other introductory chapters, e.g., history of the HAB binational program (Allen) and public outreach (Brown), and appendices on sources of information. Production of the guide was supported by the Environmental Protection Agency Gulf of Mexico Program through a binational program with Mexico, the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, the Florida Institute of Oceanography, and other sources. This binational ef-

fort is edited by Karen Steidinger and Maria Esther Meave del Castillo and will be available for free over the internet as a download.

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***Karenia mikimotoi*, a rare species in Hong Kong waters, associated with a recent massive fish kill**

Potentially toxic microalgae belonging to the genus *Karenia* occur all over the world. Although they can be detected occasionally in Hong Kong coastal waters, they had never bloomed before causing massive fish kills. From late-December 2015 to mid-February 2016, fish killing incidents were reported from several fish cultivation zones in Tolo Harbour and Long Harbour, Hong Kong (Fig. 1). At the very beginning (December 14, 2015), algal blooms mainly formed by *Karenia mikimotoi* (Fig. 2A) with a lower density of *Karenia cf papilionacea* (Fig. 2B) were found in fish cultivation zones and nearby waters in Yim Tin Tsai (Tolo Harbour) (Fig. 3). New affected cultivation areas were reported to the east in Lo Fu Wat and off Tolo Channel to Long Harbour (Hoi Ha Wan, Kau Lau Wan and Sham Wan), and offshore (Tap Mun, and O Pui Tong further north). By mid-February 2016, accumulated fish loss was nearly 221 t, mainly including Sabah grouper, green grouper and giant grouper. The only thing the mariculturists could do was just to collect and dispose of the dead

fish. Mariculturists from culture zones that were not yet affected were advised to consider early harvesting to minimize the associated risks and loss. [1]

Karenia mikimotoi can produce hemolysins and ichthyotoxins, while *Karenia papilionacea* can produce neurotoxic brevetoxins which cause neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) in humans and other mammals. [2, 3] However, the exact fish killing mechanism of these algal species is still under investigation.

In order to explore the probable cause of the fish killing incident, four sampling points including Tai Po Waterfront Park (TPWP), Lam Tsuen River estuary (LTR), Shing Mun River estuary (SMR) and Yim Tin Tsai (YTT) were chosen for further investigation (Fig. 3). Seawater samples were taken from these four sampling points on 4 January 2016 and a variety of parameters measured. The seawater qualities from four sampling points mostly achieved the Water Quality Objectives (WQOs) standard, except that the ammonia levels of TPWP and LTR were slightly higher

Fig. 2. Micrographs (X1000) of *Karenia* specimens from Yim Tin Tsai, (Tolo Harbor, Hong Kong, collected in December 2015. A. *Karenia mikimotoi*; B. *Karenia cf papilionacea*.

than that of the standard (0.021 mg/L) [4]. In addition, the fish kill was not due to virus contamination. Viral nervous necrosis (VNN) and red sea bream iri-

Fig. 1 Dead fishes found near Yam Mun Tsai fish cultivation zone, Hong Kong December 23, 2015.

Fig. 3. Cultivation areas in Hong Kong affected by fish kills and location of sampling stations (▲) in January 4, 2016: Tai Po Waterfront Park (TPWP), Lam Tsuen River (LTR), Shing Mun River (SMR) and Yim Tin Tsai (YTT).

doviral (RSIV) viral tests were done by Hong Kong Agriculture, Fisheries and Conservation Department (AFCD), and both of them showed negative results (AFCD, pers.com.).

Both potential toxin producers, *Karenia mikimotoi* and *Karenia cf papilionacea*, were found in seawater samples from the four sampling points. The cell densities of the two species were within the range of 10 to 40 cells mL⁻¹. Hence, an acute fish-toxicity test, with *Oryzias melastigma* (marine medaka) used as target species, was carried out for 96 hours with seawater collected from the four points. No mortality or abnormal behavior was observed either in fishes exposed to the seawater samples or in fish exposed to the artificial seawater (control).

From all the results above, the fish kills should not be attributed either to changes in environmental conditions (e.g. drastic change of pH or dissolved oxygen) or to virus contamination. Although *Karenia mikimotoi* and *Karenia cf papilionacea* were found in the seawater samples from all sampling points, their cell densities did not reach bloom levels. Therefore, they cannot be ex-

cluded as the causative species of the fish kills barely based on the fish exposure experiments conducted.

Karenia species seldom appear in Hong Kong coastal area. To investigate the relationship between air temperature and microalgal blooms, the temperature records from December 2015 to February 2016 were obtained from the Hong Kong Observatory (HKO) [5]. A relationship was found between increasing cell densities of *Karenia* species and the falling followed by sudden rising of air temperature values. For example, the air temperature dropped 11.2 °C between January 21, 2016 (16.2 °C) and January 24, 2016 (4.0 °C), and suddenly raised 12.3 °C on January 28, 2016 (16.3 °C). During this time, according to seawater analysis results disclosed by AFCD, cell densities of *Karenia mikimotoi* increased to 4,680 cells mL⁻¹ and 5,267 cells mL⁻¹ on January 29, 2016 and January 30, 2016 respectively. This trend (sudden falling followed by rising of air temperature coinciding with blooming of *Karenia* species) was also found in the periods December 2, 2015 to January 6, 2016 and December 24, 2015 to January 3, 2016. In the

case of *Karenia cf papilionacea*, this trend was observed between December 24, 2015 and January 3, 2016. Several blooming species of *Karenia* have been reported from Hong Kong waters in the last twenty years. However, they were never associated with fish mortalities. Abrupt (falling and quick rising) changes of air temperature maybe the critical factor that triggered the blooms and fish killing events.

In summary, two potentially ichthyotoxic species, *Karenia mikimotoi* and *Karenia cf papilionacea*, bloomed in Hong Kong coastal from December 2015 to February 2016 and were associated with mass mortalities of fish. The fish kills could not be attributed either to changes in physical-chemical parameters or to virus contamination. However, sudden and drastic temperature changes may have been related to the microalgal blooming and toxin production mechanism. For further investigation, monocultures of *Karenia mikimotoi* and *Karenia cf papilionacea* will be established, and subsequent fish exposure to blooming levels of the algal species will be conducted. Studies of environmental factors, especially on temperature change, will also be needed to investigate the triggers for algal blooming and toxin production.

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Low dissolved oxygen concentration as the triggering factor of fish mass mortalities during algal bloom incidents in Jakarta Bay, Indonesia

Fig. 1. Map of Jakarta Bay and the location of the algal bloom and fish kill events (red circle).

Recently, the recurrence of algal blooms has had a negative impact on fisheries in Jakarta bay and resulted in the mass mortality of wild fish in three locations (Fig. 1). These algal blooms developed

in the transition period from the dry to the rainy season (October to December). The fish kills occurred on October 28, 2015 in Pari Island, on November 28, 2015 in Ancol Beach and on Decem-

ber 13, 2015 in Muara Angke. A large number of dead fish appeared spreading along the shore of the three locations after the bloom incident (Fig. 2). Most of the fish seemed impacted by oxygen depletion and were observed floating in surface waters in the early morning before sunrise. According to local people and fishermen, there were water discolorations a few days before the fish kill incident. They noted that the color of the surface waters become red-brownish around Ancol beach and Muara Angke, while in Pari Island, they changed to red-green.

The collection of water samples and measurements of environmental factors were conducted after the bloom incident. These data showed that the phytoplankton community in Pari Island was dominated by *Trichodesmium*, in Ancol by *Alexandrium* while samples from Muara Angke were dominated by *Skeletonema* (Fig. 3). It is a surprise that *Alexandrium* was found as the dominant species in samples collected from Ancol beach. This is the first record of a bloom of this genus in these waters. However, it is still unknown whether this species was the only bloom species involved in the event in Ancol beach as the samples were collected a few days after these fish kills. *Skeletonema* and *Chaetoceros* regularly form blooms in Jakarta Bay and are considered to have an important role in the ecology of these waters.

During these events, the seawa-

Fig 2. Some photographs of dead fish caused by algal blooms in Jakarta Bay.

ter temperature ranged from 28.30 to 29.90 °C, and salinity from 29 to 33 psu. The concentration of phosphate and nitrate in Ancol beach ranged from 0.004 to 0.032 mg L⁻¹ and 0.139 to 0.374 mg L⁻¹ respectively, and of phosphate and nitrate in Muara Angke from 0.05 to

0.19 mg L⁻¹ and 0.09 to 0.78 mg L⁻¹, respectively. These concentrations exceeded the standard limits based on regulations implemented by the Indonesian Ministry of Environment (2004), i.e., 0.008 mg L⁻¹ for nitrate and 0.015 mg L⁻¹ for phosphate. There was no

measurement of environmental parameters in Pari Island during the event.

The concentration of dissolved oxygen (DO) in Ancol beach ranged from 0.01 to 1.47 mg L⁻¹, and in Muara Angke from 1.0 to 2.0 ppm, respectively. Generally, the concentration of dissolved oxygen in ocean waters is typically between 7 and 8 mg L⁻¹. If concentrations fall below 4 mg L⁻¹, the organisms will begin to react, with mobile organisms either avoiding or migrating out of the area. Waters with less than 2 mg L⁻¹ of dissolved oxygen is termed hypoxic and unable to support most forms of life. So it is most likely that the cause of fish kills in Jakarta Bay was due to the very low concentration of dissolved oxygen in the waters.

The intensity and distribution of algal blooms in Jakarta Bay has increased recently and a solution is required to address this natural phenomenon. One of the causes can be anthropogenic pollution which causes eutrophication of the bay [4]. Nevertheless, it is important to note that these blooms are not always accompanied by fish mortalities, except if their occurrence coincides with the period of lowest mean sea level (LMSL) during night time.

Fig 3. Photographs of the dominant genera after bloom incidents in Ancol beach: Alexandrium (A); Pari Island: Trichodesmium (B) and Muara Angke: Skeletonema (C) and (D).

Fig 4. Tide levels during bloom events in Jakarta Bay. Tide level in Pari Island: October 25 (blue), Ancol Beach: November 24 (red) and Muara Angke: December 12 (grey). Fish kills occurred in October 28, November 28 and December 13, 2015 coinciding with periods of lowest sea level.

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A *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* Margalef bloom in the channels of Marina Hemingway, La Habana, Cuba

Fig. 1. Location of Marina Hemingway in Cuba

Cochlodinium polykrikoides Margalef [1] formed a conspicuous bloom in Marina Hemingway, west of La Habana city, Cuba. Marina Hemingway is formed by four interconnected artificial channels of 30 x 800 m parallel to the open coast, a mean depth of 5m, with a common connection to the sea (Fig. 1). No freshwater inputs exist in the marina and tidal water exchange is very limited due to the length of the channels. Water discolorations (Fig. 2), first detected on September 5, 2015 (1.8×10^6 cells L^{-1}) persisted for more than a week and 18

days later densities still were as high as 7.5×10^5 cell L^{-1} . Marina Hemingway is an important tourist (yachting) resource. There were no apparent deleterious effects in marine life, and there are no cultivation resources to be affected in the area, but the bloom caused was social alarm.

The bloom appeared and was maintained under sunny and calmed weather conditions, with seawater temperatures of 30-32 °C, salinity 32-36 and pH 7.2-7.8, and declined following two days of torrential rain.

Fig 2. Water discoloration due to *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* in one of the channels of Marina Hemingway.

Fig 3. *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*. A-B Light microscopy micrographs of a four-celled chain at different focus: s, sulcus; c cingulum; e, eyespot; chl, rod-shaped chloroplasts.

Samples were taken to the plankton laboratory at the Centro de Investigaciones Pesqueras and observed under a MOTIC BA210 microscope, coupled to a digital camera, at 100x and 400x magnification. Images were processed with the software MOTIC Images-2000, version 1.2

The cells appeared mainly in chains of two to four cells. The cingulum encircled the cell almost twice, and the sulcus could be observed as a very thin line parallel to the cingulum and just beneath it (Fig. 3). Each cell had a reddish eyespot on the dorsal side, and rod-shaped chloroplasts. These morphological characteristics permitted the differentiation from the close species *Cochlodinium fulvescens* Iwataki, Kawami et Matsuoka [2].

C. polykrikoides was first described from samples collected in Bahía Fosforescente, Puerto Rico [1]. This bay became famous for having spectacular bioluminescent red tides caused by *Pyrodinium bahamense* which bloomed together with *C. polykrikoides*. The bay is formed by three branches in a mangrove ecosystem with a small connection to the sea. Like in Marina Hemingway, its restricted circulation caused limited dilution of the blooms. Blooms of *C. polykrikoides* have also been recorded in Bahía de Cienfuegos, southwest coast of Cuba, where they were associated with mass mortalities of marine organisms, such as oysters, crabs and fishes [3].

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Prorocentrum lima and Prorocentrum balticum blooms in Cartagena de Indias, Colombian Caribbean

Fig. 1. Cartagena de Indias sampling sites during the algal bloom on December 2015.

Cartagena de Indias, declared as “Heritage of Humanity” by UNESCO in November 1984, is situated in the Caribbean, and represents the most important tourist and historic district of Colombia. Due to its geographical location, different industrial and port activities take place there. However, its architectural, cultural and gastronomic richness positions it as a preferred national and international tourist destination.

Cartagena Bay (10° 26' - 10° 16' N and 75° 30' - 75° 35' W) is part of a semi-closed estuarine system of 82 km² and 16 m average depth [1]. Tierra Bomba island separates the bay from the Caribbean Sea, leaving two communication channels: “Bocagrande” in the north-east and “Bocachica” to the southeast. The northern end, called internal bay, has no direct communication with the Caribbean Sea. Cartagena Bay receives water rich in nutrients and sediments through the Dique Canal, an artificial branch of the Magdalena River [2].

During late December 2015, a red water discoloration occurred in the northern part of Cartagena bay (internal bay, Fig.1). On December 21 and 22, five surface phytoplankton samples were collected each day and fixed with neutral formaldehyde (4%, with sodium tetraborate) solution. Samples (10 mL) were examined using an inverted

microscope (X600) according to the Utermöhl quantitative method.

No unpleasant odors or dead organisms were observed or reported during the algal bloom. On December 21, the total phytoplankton cell density ranged from 1.67 x 10⁶ to 7.56 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 2). Blooms of *Prorocentrum lima* and *Prorocentrum balticum*, with population densities of 0.72 - 3.56 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ and 0.70 - 3.58 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ respectively, were identified as the cause of the discoloration. Other accompanying species were *Tripod furca*, *Prorocentrum gracile*, *Protoperdinium pellucidum*, *Skeletonema costatum*, *Thalassionema nitzschioides*, *Chaetoceros curvisetus*,

Fig. 2. Phytoplankton population densities during the algal bloom on December 2015. Each bar corresponds to an observation. Samples collected on December 21 and 22.

Ch. compressus and *Guinardia striata*; which presented a total population density between 0.41 x 10⁶ and 0.1 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 2).

On December 22, the bloom remained in the same area but the cell density was greater than before, ranging from 10.16 x 10⁶ to 5.51 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹. *P. lima* and *P. balticum* population densities, 2.1 - 4.5 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ and 3.2 - 5.4 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ respectively, were also higher. Of the species found, only *P. lima*, usually a benthic species, has been reported as a potentially toxic dinoflagellate, causing diarrhea in humans. This algal bloom should serve as a warning to the environmental authorities and the tourist industry of Cartagena de Indias. Only in the last tourist season of 2015, it is estimated that the city hosted about 450,000 tourists, 11% of which were international visitors coming from Europe, the United States, the Caribbean and South America.

The causes of the algal bloom in Cartagena are unclear, but dredging activities in Bocachica and the main channel during December 2015, along with high water temperatures (30,2 °C ± 0,12 SD), may have been the factors promoting such a *P. lima* bloom. It is important to increase the local understanding of the dynamics of algal blooms in the region in order to improve the ability to cope with its impacts which could be highly negative for the population and industry.

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Blooms of *Cylindrospermopsis cuspis* in oyster beds of Términos Lagoon, southeastern Gulf of Mexico

Fig. 1. Study area and location of sampling stations

Términos Lagoon is one of the key ecosystems in the southern Gulf of Mexico and has been the focus of both national and international attention because of its ecological and economic importance and due to the potential impact exerted on this ecosystem by human activities [1].

As part of the project to describe the phytoplankton community with an emphasis on harmful species, six stations were monitored monthly in oyster beds of Términos Lagoon (Fig. 1), from August 2012 to September 2013. These are the areas of natural oyster harvesting to supply the local market for human consumption. In October 2012, a bloom of the cyanobacterium *Cylindrospermopsis cuspis* Komárek et Kling, reaching 1.3×10^6 cells L^{-1} , caused the temporary closure of the extraction activity of *Crassostrea virginica* Gmelin for 15 days. This bloom lasted until November 2012 (Fig. 2). Salinity was 7.3 and temperature 27 °C. No discoloration of water was observed. Cyanobacterial abundance increased to 10^6 cells L^{-1} in October, and small peaks were also observed during the rest of the year. Among cyanobacteria, the genus *Anabaena* Bory de Saint-Vincent occurred throughout the study period, with a maximal density of 1.9×10^6 cells L^{-1} and a minimum of 3.6×10^4 cells L^{-1} , without any apparent harmful effect.

Both taxa have been previously recorded in the fluvial-lagoons Pom-Atasta and Palizada-East adjacent to the study area, with densities up to 10^3 cells L^{-1} [2]. It should be noted that densities were lower than those reported in this study because they were found in winter. *Cylindrospermopsis cuspis* was reported in the region of Tuxtlas, in the southern part of the state of Veracruz [3-4], without apparent toxic events.

Cyanobacterial blooms have been recurrent in some lagoons of the Gulf of Mexico. In Catemaco Lake in Veracruz, a bloom of *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii* (Wolosz.) Seenayya et Subba Raju occurred, causing a high bioaccumulation of toxins (cylindrospermopsin and paralytic shellfish toxins) throughout the food chain [5-6]. This species contributed more than 90% of the total abundance of cyanobacteria, and it was also dominant in two other lakes from

Fig. 2. *Cylindrospermopsis cuspis* from Términos Lagoon, southeastern Gulf of Mexico

Los Tuxtlas region in the state of Veracruz, Nixtamalapan and Encantada [7]. In October 2013, in the Alvarado Lagoon System, Veracruz, a bloom of *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* (Bréb. ex Bornet et Flahault) P. Wacklin, L. Hoffmann et J. Komárek was observed, with a maximum abundance of 9.1×10^7 cells L^{-1} , but in that case there were no harmful effects reported [8].

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HABs in Paradise

Fig. 1. Sampling sites at Raoul Island, Kermadec Islands (images by Charlie Bedford)

Ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) is caused by species in the dinoflagellate genus *Gambierdiscus*. CFP has been called a neglected tropical disease, but recently research funds have become available and new research projects are being planned. Cawthron Institute has a small project on 'Climate change and HABs' within its government-funded Safe New Zealand Seafood programme. The main driver for this research is the potential for CFP risk to increase in New Zealand's northern sub-tropical waters as our oceans warm up. *Gambierdiscus* and the related *Fukuyoa* have already been reported in Northland, New Zealand, although in low concentrations [1]. Research has already been carried out in the Cook Islands, in collaboration with the University of Technology Sydney, Australia (contact: Prof Shauna Murray) and with Cook Islands researchers (contact: Dr Teina Rongo, Ministry for Climate Change). CFP occurs regularly in the Southern Cooks and intensive sampling there, using new molecular tools (for example, metabarcoding) and new chemical detection methods [2], has determined that the main causa-

tive organism there is the ciguatoxin producer, *G. polynesiensis* [3]. Two new *Gambierdiscus* species from the Cook Islands, which produce uncharacterised toxins, are currently being described.

The Kermadec Island group lies between the Cook Islands and New Zealand and falls within New Zealand's economic zone. A recent announcement by the New Zealand government has promised that 620,000 km² in the Kermadec region is to become a fully protected, 'no take' ocean sanctuary. It will become one of the world's largest and most significant protected areas. Previous samples received at Cawthron Institute from Raoul Island, Kermadec Islands, contained *Gambierdiscus* cells, but these failed to survive in culture (Fig. 1) [4]. A recent expedition (November 2015) to the Kermadec Islands, led by Dr Tom Trnski, Auckland Museum, resulted in sea water samples from Meyer Island, which lies to the north east of the larger Raoul Island. The concentrations of *Gambierdiscus* in these samples, collected from macroalgae and coralline turfs, suggests blooms of this genus were occurring at depths of

12 to 17 m. Preliminary investigations showed the presence of *G. australes* (which was dominant), *G. carpenteri* and *G. polynesiensis*. More research into the Kermadec Island samples is being carried out and toxin production will be determined once cultures are fully established.

The risk of CFP occurring in New Zealand is increased by these findings, not just through the presence of blooms in New Zealand's territorial waters, but through fish passing between the Cook Islands via the Kermadec Island group to New Zealand. Further sampling will be carried out in the future to assess changes in the occurrence of *Gambierdiscus* in New Zealand. Comparisons with 'base-line' samples from Northland (2014) will be made based on metabarcoding data analyses. This will be of particular interest with the current El Niño climate event, expected to be one of the strongest on record.

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A first study of the diversity of the *Tripos* genus in the marine waters of Belize and the Gulf of Honduras

Fig. 1. Sampling sites (filled circles) off Belize and the Gulf of Honduras (Bahia de Amatique). 1. Off Livingston Sea Buoy; 2. Ox Tongue Bight; 3. Off Tres Puntas 4. Off Big Creek; 5. South Long Coco Cay; 6. North Long Coco Cay; 7. South Water Cay 8. Outside Barrier Reef 9. Tobacco Range

Dinoflagellates are common components of the tropical phytoplankton and some can form harmful algal blooms. A first study of the biodiversity of the dinoflagellate genus *Tripos* (Bory de Saint-Vincent) from Belize's barrier reef and the nearby Gulf of Honduras was performed between 2010 and 2013. The reef is an endangered UNESCO world heritage site and the region has extremely important and diverse ecosystems [1]. Species within the *Tripos* genus can cause serious ecosystem stress when they form dense blooms [2,3] and can also be considered as valuable monitors of ocean currents and ocean warming [4,5]. Prior to this study there was little information about the diversity of the *Tripos* genus (recently re-named from *Neoceratium* /*Ceratium* [6]) in these waters.

A sub-surface, 53- μ m mesh, plankton net was towed at nine sampling

sites (Fig. 1) inside and outside Belize's barrier reef and the nearby Gulf of Honduras (Bahia de Amatique) during the months of March and April from 2010 to 2013 inclusive. Approximately 5 m³ of water was filtered at each site. Twenty seven species and sub species were found which were similar to those reported for other tropical seas and in the nearby southern Gulf of Mexico [7] with the additional records of *T. contortus* var. *robustus*, *T. vultur* f. *japonicus*, and *T. reflexus* [6,8]. Some species were rarely observed so only one record is given.

Un-stained light microscope photographs of the species listed in Table 1 are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The bracketed numbers in the figures are

individual cell width and cell length (width x length) and the antapical horn span (span was measured only in cells where the antapical horns curved towards the apical horn). Cell width is the most reliable of these measurements as broken horns, undulating focal planes and cell debris can all compromise measurements of cell span and length.

In conclusion the study will act as a baseline for the zonal biodiversity and distribution of the *Tripos* species inside and outside Belize's barrier reef and the adjacent Gulf of Honduras (Bahia de Amatique). This is important as some cosmopolitan species of the genus reported here – *T. furca*, *T. fusus* and *T. muellerii* (Table 1) are known to cause harmful (discolouration and hypoxia) algal blooms. The tropical species of the genus in Table 1 could also be used as biological indicators of global warming [5].

Species	Width (μ m)	Length (μ m)	Span (μ m)
1. <i>T. arcuatus</i> f. <i>karstenii</i>	80.00	420.00	220.00
2. <i>T. bigelowii</i>	25.00		
3. <i>T. contortus</i> var. <i>subcontortus</i> * and	66.67 \pm 4.29	365.00 \pm 68.74	176.8 \pm 9.94
4. <i>T. contortus</i> var. <i>saltans</i> (pooled data)	(n=12)	(n=12)	(n=10)
5. <i>T. contortus</i> var. <i>robustus</i>	100.00	404.00	320.00
6. <i>T. contrarius</i> (could be morphotype of <i>T. trichoceros</i>)	48.00 \pm 12.81	335.00 \pm 68.62	362.00 \pm 71.14
7. <i>T. dens</i>	67 \pm 3.83	253.00 \pm 73.64	275.00 \pm 25.17
8. <i>T. extensus</i>	(n=4)	(n=4)	(n=4)
9. <i>T. furca</i> var. <i>eugrammus</i>	25.25 \pm 2.76	1387.38 \pm 368.65	
10. <i>T. furca</i> var. <i>hircus</i>	(n=8)	(n=8)	
11. <i>T. fusus</i>	27.53 \pm 5.33	166.14 \pm 45.11	
12. <i>T. gibberus</i> f. <i>dispar</i>	(n=21)	(n=21)	
13. <i>T. hexacanthus</i>	42.73 \pm 4.48	236.67 \pm 50.46	
14. <i>T. horridus</i> var. <i>buceros</i>	(n=9)	(n=9)	
15. <i>T. inflatus</i>	20.63 \pm 2.75	532.91 \pm 104.20	
16. <i>T. kofoidii</i>	(n=6)	(n=6)	
17. <i>T. longirostrus</i>	60.00		112.00
18. <i>T. macroceros</i> var. <i>gallicus</i>	70.43 \pm 7.07	474.67 \pm 239.00	
19. <i>T. massiliense</i> var. <i>armatus</i>	(n=2)	(n=2)	
20. <i>T. muellerii</i> f. <i>atlanticus</i> **	36.00	172.00	120.00
21. <i>T. muellerii</i> var. <i>brevis</i>	24.80 \pm 3.35	614.00 \pm 100.90	
22. <i>T. muellerii</i> var. <i>tripodioides</i>	(n=5)	(n=5)	
23. <i>T. reflexus</i>	23.60 \pm 2.19	135.40 \pm 10.43	
24. <i>T. symmetricus</i>	(n=5)	(n=5)	
25. <i>T. teres</i>	24.00	610.00	
26. <i>T. trichoceros</i>	40.00		
27. <i>T. vultur</i> f. <i>japonicus</i>	63.71 \pm 9.51	421.00 \pm 101.98	350.29 \pm 69.13
	(n=28)	(n=24)	(n=21)
	67.00 \pm 6.86	222.30 \pm 25.39	172.21 \pm 11.60
	(n=36)	(n=33)	(n=19)
	68.44 \pm 6.15	231.75 \pm 26.28	154.25 \pm 15.54
	(n=9)	(n=8)	(n=8)
	60.83 \pm 5.53	254.91 \pm 36.31	154.90 \pm 23.48
	(n=11)	(n=11)	(n=10)
	70.00	240.00	200.00
	62.80 \pm 3.35	138.40 \pm 14.31	128.00
	(n=5)	(n=5)	
	38.40 \pm 2.19	134.00 \pm 25.14	
	(n=5)	(n=5)	
	44.11 \pm 13.49	304 \pm 47.46	234.22 \pm 57.14
	(n=18)	(n=17)	(n=9)
	66.00 \pm 2.83	368 \pm 45.25	118.00 \pm 25.46
	(n=2)	(n=2)	(n=2)

* *C. contortum* var. *contortum* [7] ** *C. tripos* var. *tripos* [7]

Table 1. Means \pm standard deviation (SD) of cell width, length and span of the various *Tripos* species obtained from the tropical marine waters of Belize and the Gulf of Honduras. Observation numbers are given in parenthesis (n). (The *T. contortus* mean value is the pooled data. Span measurements taken from the right antapical horn elbow to the left horn tip.).

Fig. 2. 1. *T. massiliense* var. *armatus* (70 x 460 μ m, span 315 μ m). 2. *T. trichoceros* (40 x 248 μ m, span 312 μ m). 3. *T. dens* (64 x 260 μ m, span, left antapical horn tip to right horn tip, 280 μ m). VV. 4. *T. contortus* var. *subcontortus* (64 x 400 μ m, span, left horn tip to right horn elbow, 168 μ m). (**C. contortum* var. *contortum* [7]). VV. 5. *T. contortus* var. *saltans* (68 x 380 μ m, span, left horn tip to right horn elbow, 180 μ m). DV. 6. *T. vultur* f. *japonicus* (60 x 400 μ m). DV. 6a. *T. vultur* f. *japonicus* (64 x 336 μ m, span 136 μ m). DV. 7. *T. contrarius* (40 x 320 μ m). DV. Note: *T. contrarius* could be a morphotype of *T. trichoceros*. 8. *T. arcuatus* f. *karstenii* (80 x 420 μ m, span 420 μ m). DV. 9. *T. contortus* var. *robustus* ([8], Fig. 67), (100 x 404 μ m, span 320 μ m). DV. 10. *T. horridus* var. *buceros* (36 x 172 μ m, span 120 μ m). DV. 11. and 11a. *T. reflexus* (70 x 240 μ m, span of antapical horns, 200 μ m). 12. *T. hexacanthus* (70 x 240 μ m, span 200 μ m). DV. 12a. *T. hexacanthus* (60 x 332 μ m). DV. VV (Ventral View). DV (Dorsal View).

Fig. 3. 1. *T. muellerii* f. *atlanticus* (62 x 240 μ m). (***C. tripos* var. *tripos* [7]). VV. 2. *T. muellerii* var. *brevis* (76 x 204 μ m, span 164 μ m). DV. 3. *T. muellerii* var. *tripodioides* (64 x 212 μ m, span 120 μ m). VV. 4. *T. symmetricus* (64 x 160 μ m, span 128 μ m). VV. 5. *T. gibberus* f. *dispar* (cell body width 60 μ m, span 112 μ m). VV. 6. and 6a. *T. fusus* (20 x 620 μ m). VV. 7. and 7a. *T. extensus*, long horns, (28 x 1120 μ m). VV. Also in 7. see *T. massiliense* (68 x 370 μ m). VV. 8 and 8a. *T. longirostrus*. Left antapical horn curved to left, (24 x 610 μ m). DV. 9 and 9a. *T. inflatus* (26 x 400 μ m). DV. 10. *T. bigelowii* (cell width 25 μ m). VV. 11. *T. furca* var. *eugrammus* (36 x 240 μ m). VV. 12. *T. furca* var. *hircus* (44 x 216 μ m). DV. 13. *T. kofoidii* (26 x 143 μ m). VV. 14. *T. teres* (40 x 98 μ m). DV. VV (Ventral View). DV (Dorsal View).

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IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae

The Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae has for a decade now been available on the internet (www.marinespecies.org/hab). The list presently comprises a total of 149 species: 20 diatom species, 8 haptophyte species, 84 dinoflagellate species, 4 raphidophytes, 3 dictyochophytes and 30 cyanobacteria. Most work on the list has recently centered on adding cyanobacteria. These were not previously included but we have, assisted by Gertrud Cronberg in Lund, Sweden, started updating this part of the list. The procedure is the same as with other species. The original literature on toxic events caused by a given species is checked and, if the evidence for a toxic effect is accepted and the species appears to be correctly identified and named, it is added to the list. In case of doubt about the causative species for a harmful event (for example when the plankton contains several species), the species is usually not accepted for inclusion in the list. Gertrud Cronberg and Helene Annadotter have kindly allowed us to include in the list the excellent light micrographs of harmful cyanobacteria from their book [1]

When fully updated, the list of cyanobacteria is expected to double. Before continuing with the list and the taxonomic problems associated with it, I would like to draw the attention to some information I learnt from working with the list and which, although not completely new, is probably not generally known. It relates to what is probably the most serious problem associated with cyanobacteria in the sea (in brackish water), the large blooms of the filamentous species *Nodularia spumigena*, not least in the Baltic. Such blooms are news on Danish TV every summer, and we usually warn people not to swim in the water during heavy blooms. However, during the work with the list I came across a number of articles containing much more disturbing

information. It is well known that *Nodularia* produces the tumor-promoting pentapeptid nodularin, but these toxins have now been found to accumulate in both blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) and in the liver and muscles within the two fish species examined, flounder (*Platichthys flesus*) and round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*). I refer the reader to recent studies from the Bay of Gdansk in Poland, cited in the IOC List.

The IOC List generally comprises species known to or suspected to produce toxins, which have harmful effect on humans and/or fish. For many fish killers the toxin has not been identified with certainty, but these species have been included in the list anyway due to their known toxic impact on the fish. Blooms of non-toxic algae, which may cause fish kills in fish pens and among bottom invertebrates due to oxygen depletion, are not included, nor are species that physically irritate fish gills because of spines (the setae of the diatom *Chaetoceros*) and cause loss of fish.

The IOC List was begun as a list of correct names for harmful species. However, there is no agreement among taxonomists as to what constitutes a species. We have taken a pragmatic view, as the list is being used for monitoring, and academic matters (no matter how interesting!) are kept to a minimum. Taxonomic changes are therefore treated in a very conservative way, name changes are made only when they are supported by strong evidence, which makes it unlikely that the change will have to be rolled back when more data become available. Changes in the names cannot be completely avoided. A case in point comes from two recent large monographs, not on algae, but on a different biological subject, the conifers. Both authors described and discussed all the conifers of the world. However, one author—the lumper—considers 545 species to be present, the other—the splitter—splits them into 615

species. The problem is how to define a subspecies, a variety, etc. The authors also differ in the number of genera present in the world, and in several generic names. These problems relate to very large plants, not to microscopical algae.

We cannot avoid name changes completely but we can aim at keeping the number down. Personally I have over the years developed skepticism when the number of species in a genus is concluded solely from single- or a few-gene phylogenetic trees, rather than from morphological characters, believed to be the results of numerous genes. Among recent changes in the list is that the two species of the raphidophyte *Chattonella*, *C. ovata* and *C. antiqua*, have now been reduced to variety level, and the species *C. marina* therefore now comprises three varieties, var. *antiqua*, var. *ovata* and var. *marina*. The varieties can usually be distinguished by cell shape or molecular signature, but overlaps occur. We recognize, however, that it is a matter of personal preference whether to treat the three taxa as species or varieties.

Merging of several species of *Microcystis*, advocated recently from studies of a few genes, is not accepted in the list. Several of the species selected for merging are morphologically distinct, casting doubt on the usefulness of the molecular data used for species identification.

Finally, a pledge: While the main purpose of the IOC List is to provide correct names, we also try in the list to provide information on other issues such as toxic effects. This is a field in which new findings are made regularly and we are grateful for any new information: new toxic species, new studies on toxic effects.

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Plankton Planet

Plankton, which includes all organisms drifting with the currents (from virus to animals), are the basis of the oceanic food chain and produce ~50% of the oxygen we breathe. Plankton dynamics are primarily influenced by oceans/atmosphere's physics and key environmental drivers such as temperature and CO₂ concentration. As a result, planktonic organisms are excellent indicator of the effect that stressors such as pollution and climate change have on our oceans.

Currently, all oceanographic models aimed at predicting global ecological changes lack good quality and high resolution biological data on oceanic plankton. There is a clear and urgent need for innovative approaches enabling collection and analysis of plankton biodiversity and distribution data over much larger spatio-temporal scales than is currently possible. These

data would bring the knowledge of plankton ecosystems closer to the one we have from terrestrial and coastal benthic systems and thus provide an invaluable resource to detect, quantify, and predict global ecological changes in the Earth system.

Plankton Planet (P2) is an international project (France, New Zealand, USA) that promotes citizen-based sampling of marine plankton to measure the genetic biodiversity and biological health of the world oceans on relevant spatial and temporal scales. The team has developed very simple sampling tools and protocols allowing volunteer citizen-sailors (planktonauts) to isolate total DNA from plankton communities while sailing and without any specialised expertise. Samples are then sent to scientists who process them using massive sequencing of DNA barcodes (metabarcoding). Analyses of the me-

tabarcodes allow then to detect and quantify all eukaryotic plankton biota in any given sample, providing critical data to measure biodiversity and species interaction networks over space and time. This is a revolutionary approach to biological oceanography, which capitalizes on the thousands of citizens sailing around the world every day. It forgoes the need to rely on high carbon-footprint and extremely costly research vessels, and allows rigorous surveys of global oceanic plankton over spatio-temporal scales that have not previously been possible.

See more at: www.planktonplanet.org

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A mandala of plankton diversity. Photo credit: Christian Sardet. Plankton Chronicles From "Plankton - Wonders of the Drifting World" Univ. Chicago Press 2015.

GlobalHAB – a new initiative in the HAB community

GlobalHAB, the new international scientific programme on Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) was launched this year. The first meeting of the newly formed GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) was hosted at the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) in Oban, Scotland from 8 to 10 March 2016. GlobalHAB is an initiative under the auspices of the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC). GlobalHAB builds on the wealth of scientific results delivered through the recently completed Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (GEOHAB) programme (www.geohab.info).

The steering committee has representatives from across the globe (Fig. 1): Elisa Berdalet (Chair, Spain), Neil Banas (UK), Michele Burford (Australia), Chris Gobler (USA), Bengt Karlson (Sweden), Raphael Kudela (USA), Po Teen Lim (Malaysia), Lincoln Mackenzie (New Zealand), Marina Montresor (Italy), and Kedong Yin (China). Liaisons from ICES (Eileen Bresnan), IPHAB (Gires Usup), PICES and ISSHA (Vera Trainer), and SAMS (Keith Davidson) participated in the meeting and are helping develop the GlobalHAB plans. Henrik Enevoldsen

from IOC and Ed Urban from SCOR assisted the GlobalHAB SSC and provided input from sponsoring organizations.

In this first meeting, with a positive and active atmosphere, the participants defined the fundamental elements that will structure the GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan is expected to be completed by June 2016:

The **mission** of this cutting-edge programme is *to improve understanding, prediction, management and mitigation of HABs in aquatic ecosystems*.

The scientific **goals** of GlobalHAB include:

- To address the scientific and societal challenges of HABs, including the environmental, human health and economic impacts, in a rapidly changing world.
- To involve participants from related fields of natural and social science, and will link with other regional and international organizations, and initiatives relevant to HABs.
- To foster intercalibration among existing methods, as well as promote the development and adoption of new technologies.
- To promote training, capacity building and communication of knowledge about HABs to society.

- To serve as a liaison between the scientific community, stakeholders and policy makers, promoting science-based decision making.

A range of **implementation activities** were identified to be undertaken in the next three years and beyond. Namely, workshops and open science meetings will specifically address toxin-related challenges (detection methods, action mode, molecular basis), evaluate the impacts of aquaculture on HAB occurrences in different regions, and ascertain the potential climate change impacts on HABs occurrence in freshwater and marine ecosystems. Science/stakeholder forums will be organized to assess the potential socio-economic impacts of HAB occurrences and to engage the medical community to improve human health protection. GlobalHAB implementation will be conducted with new linkages with the existing international and regional initiatives including IPHAB, the ICES-IOC Working Group on HAB Dynamics, PICES Section on Ecology of Harmful Algal Blooms in the North Pacific, GOOS, the IOCCG/GEOHAB Ocean Colour & HAB working group, GEO and IAEA.

The GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan will be presented at the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae in Florianopolis, Brazil in October 2016. This will be an extraordinary opportunity to involve the international community working on HABs with the new programme. As in its predecessor programme, GEOHAB, the international coordination approach to address the fundamental problem of HABs is the keystone of GlobalHAB.

GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee (SSC)

Contact: Elisa Berdalet (Chair), Institut de Ciències del Mar, Barcelona, Spain
Email: berdalet@icm.csic.es

First session of the IOCAFRICA Group of Experts on Harmful Algal Blooms

The third session of the UNESCO/IOC's Sub Commission for Africa and the Adjacent Island States, IOCAFRICA, (14-15 April 2015, Nairobi, Kenya) established a Group of Experts on Harmful Algal Blooms to develop a detailed proposal for an IOCAFRICA programme on HABs in consultation with the IOC HAB programme for consideration by the IOCAFRICA Officers and the fourth session of IOCAFRICA.

Examples were given of cyanobacteria in Egyptian waters, blooms experienced off Madagascar and the increasing incidence of *Sargassum* affecting Ghana, Cote d'Ivoire and Sierra Leone in West Africa. The rapid growth of economies in the region is likely to lead to increased incidences of HABs due to biological and chemical sources.

IOC has implemented regional activities on HABs in Africa, ranging from training in technical skills for monitoring algae and algal toxins to development of regional manuals and guides [1] and has worked with specific member states to establish national monitoring and sea food control programmes. IOC has also worked closely with IAEA on regional HAB training in Africa during the past 10 years and has a regional network on HABs in North Africa (HANA) that meets every second year depending on available funding. The IOC is in close cooperation with other UN and re-

gional organizations globally compiling data on HAB species occurrences and HAB events. There is at present no network of reporters/editors in sub Saharan Africa although this would be highly desirable. The data compilations (in the IOC databases HAEDAT and OBIS) will provide an important basis for a Global HAB Status report which is in preparation.

The meeting of the IOCAFRICA group of HAB experts was hosted by the Kenya Marine and Fisheries Research Institute (KMFRI) from 22-26 February 2016 in Mombasa, Kenya, and attended by experts from 10 African coastal countries (Fig. 1). The meeting was officially opened by Director of the Kenya Marine and Fisheries Research Institute, Dr. Renison Ruwa, who appreciated the efforts of IOC/UNESCO and IAEA for creating a platform for marine scientists to share their ideas and experiences in conserving the ocean world's resources. He noted that HABs are a global threat to living resources and have had significant impacts on the livelihood and the health of coastal communities for decades in a number of countries. He stressed that the oceans and seas connect a number of world countries and economies and a regional/ global approach to predicting and monitoring HABs is needed to protect human health and marine resources. He informed the meeting that

HAB occurrence and impacts are likely to increase in the face of emerging issues, such as climate change, increase in sea surface temperatures, eutrophication and ocean acidification, and challenged scientists that they have the responsibility to generate and provide accurate information to the decision-makers on HAB occurrences, their triggers and possible impacts.

The objectives of the meeting was to prepare an inventory of HABs related events and HAB related studies and publications in the region, as well as the development of a detailed proposal for an IOCAFRICA HABs programme. The terms of reference of the IOCAFRICA Group of Experts on HABs were:

- (i) Prepare an inventory of available capacity for HAB related studies in the region (expertise, equipment and other facilities)
- (ii) Prepare an inventory of HAB related publications from/about the region
- (iii) Compile records of HAB events for the period 2010-2015 and thereby establish a database of HAB species identified in the region and prepare a report which would both contribute to HAEDAT and the IOC Global HAB Status Report.
- (iv) Identify potential contributing factors for HAB events
- (v) Prepare a review document quantifying the scale, nature and extent of the problems associated with fish killing algae in the region.

Fig 1. Participants at the I IOCAFRICA - HAB meeting, Mombasa, Kenya, 22-26 February 2016 (Photo from the Kenya Marine and Fisheries Research Institute)

- (vi) Prepare a detailed proposal for an IOCAFRICA programme on HABs (including capacity development requirements and monitoring programme).
- (vii) Formulate a strategy for communication to and engagement of scientists and managers in Africa working with different HAB aspects, including identification of relevant partners in regional IOCAFRICA HAB activities.

Country reports were presented for Cote d'Ivoire, Egypt, Ghana, Kenya, Madagascar, Morocco, Namibia, and Tanzania. Highlights of the reports included: HAB events responsible for toxin production, PSP, ASP, lipophilic toxins in shellfish as well as fish mortality, and cyanobacteria blooms.

The group of experts agreed that members would generate regional baseline data, develop an inventory of all HABs events from 2010-2015, assess capacities and facilities to manage HABs effects (human, equipment, laws/

regulatory, programs, financial), and tabulate monitoring activities of HABs in African countries. They also agreed on the need for mapping of the occurrences of HABs with existing data, basic and advance training on phytoplankton and advanced microscopy capacity building, development of a regional HABs identification guide and the use of standardized nets for sampling benthic microalgae to fully understand HABs related issues in Africa.

The group of experts noted that HABs issues have not been prioritized despite the fact that commercial fisheries/aquaculture play a key role in food security and boosting the economy and as such there is need for documentation of possible HAB occurrences and impacts in Africa.

Other challenges facing adequate understanding of HABs related issues include the lack of adequate databases, insufficient funds, lack of awareness on HAB issues in some countries, insufficient technical capacities, poor coordination at national and regional levels,

insufficient long term commitment of governments, insufficient expertise, lack of cooperation south-south and North-south and insufficient regulations.

The participants also had a session to develop a joint work plan with the national coordinators for the International Atomic Energy Agency's project on "Applying Nuclear Analytical Techniques to Support Harmful Algal Bloom Management in the Context of Climate and Environmental Change"

References

1. Gert Hansen et al 2001. *IOC Manual and Guides 41, IOC of UNESCO 2001 (English and French) PDF*

Authors

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Hamid Taleb, HANA Chair, National Institute of Fisheries Research (INRH), 2 Rue de Tiznit, Casablanca, Morocco

The 2016 meeting of the ICES – IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics

The ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics was hosted by Dr. Raffaele Siano at the IFREMER laboratory, Brest, France from the 19th – 23rd April 2016. Fifteen delegates from ten countries attended with a further two participating by correspondence. Terms of reference addressed during the meeting included a review

of the dynamics of *Alexandrium minutum* in the bay of Brest, production of a status report of harmful algal events in the ICES area using data held in the IOC-ICES-PICES HAE-DAT database (<http://haedat.iode.org/>), experiences using molecular methods during HAB monitoring and research, and the use of trigger levels in HAB monitoring pro-

grammes. New findings included the first detection of tetrodotoxin (TTX) in Dutch waters, mercury in phytoplankton from Puck Bay, Poland, *Ostreopsis* in Spanish waters, satellite monitoring of cyanobacterial blooms in the Baltic and SPATT monitoring of lipophilic shellfish toxins on the west coast of Scotland. National reports included reports of closures for paralytic, lipophilic and amnesic shellfish toxins in Europe and observations of *Ostreopsis* in France and Spain. Cyanobacterial blooms were observed in the Baltic. A range of HAB impacts were recorded in the USA during 2015 with the extensive *Pseudo-nitzschia* bloom resulting in problems from high concentrations of domoic acid recorded along the west coast of the USA and Canada. The next WGHABD will be hosted from 25th – 28th April 2017 by Dr. Anke Kremp, Finnish Environment Institute, Helsinki, Finland.

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Fig. 1: Participants at the ICES-IOC WGHABD meeting, 19-23 April 2016, Brest, France.

Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission

Regional Training Course on Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP): Field Monitoring and Toxin Data Management. Santo Domingo, October 26 - November 6, 2015

This course was organized by IAEA as an activity of project RLA7020 *Establishing the Caribbean Observing Network for Ocean Acidification and its Impact on Harmful Algal Blooms, using Nuclear and Isotopic Techniques* in collaboration with the IOC of UNESCO, Universidad Nacional Pedro Henríquez Ureña and the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources of the Dominican Republic. Participants were from Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominican Republic, El Salvador, Guatemala, Jamaica, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, and Venezuela (Fig. 1).

The objective of the course was to improve the skills of participants in field

collection of benthic dinoflagellates (using artificial substrate and macrophytes) and sample processing prior to reviewing the taxonomy of benthic HAB (BHAB) genera. In addition data management using the Harmful Algae Event Database (HAEDAT) was addressed and an event reporting network with partners of IOC-ANCA was established.

During the first week, information was shared with the IOC working group on Benthic HABs and discussions were directed to the types of data sharing activities possible with the HAEDAT (<http://haedat.iode.org/>). Lectures on the physiology and biogeography of benthic HABs in the Caribbean region

were provided. In addition, a lecture on the international effort via IOC-International Program on Harmful Algal Blooms with the aid of FAO to have ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) declared a “neglected tropical disease”.

The objective of the second week of the workshop was to improve the skills of the participants in benthic phytoplankton field collection using both macrophytes and a new artificial substrate method (Figs 2-3) and review the taxonomy of BHAB genera. Boca Chica, approximately 32 km East of Santo Domingo, was selected as field sampling location. A number of benthic HAB species were found there including

Fig. 1. Participants in the IAEA Regional Training Course on Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) Field Monitoring and Toxin Data Management.

some *Gambierdiscus* species, and the sampling site was accessible to all participants. The gently sloping beach, less than 1.5 m depth proved a safe site for all. Hands on training was provided so participants could make their own artificial sampling devices for deployment during the next two days of field work.

Lectures on taxonomy of toxic marine benthic dinoflagellates with emphasis on *Gambierdisucs* were provided. Practical identification with the microscope was performed with pure algal cultures of six species of *Gambierdiscus* provided by the two trainers (Pat Tester and Santiago Fraga), and of other benthic dinoflagellates from the genera *Ostreopsis*, *Prorocentrum* and *Coolia*. Practical training was provided on single cells isolation with a micropipette from field samples spiked with cultured cells to start new cultures.

Cell culture media and culturing techniques were discussed in lectures. The use of Sedgewick-Rafter counting chambers was demonstrated. Time was set aside to discuss monitoring strategies and country specific needs and limitations were considered in revised monitoring plans. In addition to generating regional technical capacity in data management using the Harmful Algae Event database (HAEDAT), the workshop was an opportunity to meet with partners of IOC-ANCA to establish a network for event reporting.

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Fig. 2. A screen used as an artificial substrate, moored with a full of sand mineral-water bottle with a little buoy attached to it.

Fig 3. Sampling with the new artificial substrate method. Labeling and collection by a snorkeler.

Dear ISSHA members and other HAB experts and managers: The time for the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae (Florianópolis, Brazil, 9-14 October 2016) is approaching. The local organizers and ISSHA committees are doing their best to try to make this event more exciting than ever, in particular for young scientists attending this conference for the first time in their short career. This is the first time the HAB conference is held in South America, so it is a very special event for all our Latin American colleagues. We are pleased to invite you to participate in important decisions/activities, some of which have now become part of our traditions during the ICHA Conferences, and some others which are innovations to make the conference more proactive.

First of all, we invite you to become an ISSHA member if you are not still so. By being a member, you will get a 20% reduction in your registration fee, and most important, your contribution will help to facilitate the participation of young PhD students and/or experts from developing countries/economies in transition. The issues for which we need your help are:

1. **New! Scientific Speed Networking For Students**
2. Nominations for the Yasumoto Award and the Young Scientist Award (**Deadline May 15**)
3. Travel Awards to attend the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae (**Deadline May 15**)
4. Bids to host the 19th ICHA Conference (**Deadline July 31**)
5. Donations for the ISSHA Auction 2016.
6. Nominations for ISSHA Officers and Council members.

1. Scientific Speed Networking For Students

Panelists and Mentors: Charles Trick, Vera Trainer, Lisa Campbell, Paulo Salomon, Silvia Nascimento

ISSHA's Corner

It can be daunting to try to introduce yourself to someone at a large scientific meeting, but given the right opportunity, a quality exchange can have a lasting impression. Scientific speed dating is a twist on the popular singles speed dating phenomenon. The goal here is to foster an interactive environment between small groups of advanced scientists and students in hopes of creating some short, high impact exchanges. It's amazing what can be accomplished in just a few minutes! Join us for this workshop to start building new connections.

Time: 13:00-16:00 on Sunday, October 9 in Florianópolis Brazil

Place: ICHA 2016 Conference Hotel

Who: Open to the first 50 students who sign up (please register at the ICHA2016 website)"

2. Nominations for the Yasumoto Award and the Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award

ISSHA members are invited to submit nominations for the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award and the Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award. Further information on the appropriate profile of the nominees can be found at ISSHA website [ACHIEVEMENT AWARDS](#)

Any ISSHA member in good standing may submit nominations for either achievement award, which should include a description of the nominee's contribution (not more than one page). Please, make sure that you and your nominee have renewed your membership for the period 2016-2017. Nominations should be sent by e-mail to Drs. Marta Estrada (marta@icm.csic.es) and Pat Tester (ocean.testster@gmail.com), Co-chairs of the Committee on Achievement Awards, deadline: **May 15, 2016**. Please write "ISSHA Achievement Awards 2016" in the message subject. Nominations will be considered by the ISSHA Council, and eventual awards

will be presented during the closing ceremony by the end of the 17th ICHA Conference in Florianópolis.

3. Travel Awards to attend the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae

ISSHA will offer a limited number of travel awards for students and post-doctoral investigators to attend the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae, 9-14 October 2016, in Florianópolis, Brazil. Awards will be limited to a maximum of \$1,000 US. Successful applicants will need to demonstrate that other sources of funds are available to supplement their award. Criteria for selection and information to be included in the application letter can be found at [ISSHA TRAVEL AWARDS](#).

To apply for funds, please send the **application letter**, as a PDF File, to Dr Christine Band-Schmidt, Chair of the Committee on Travel Awards (cjband@yahoo.com) following the format available on the ISSHA website. Please write "ISSHA Travel Awards 2016" in the message subject. Applications not submitted this way may be rejected.

The deadline for receipt of applications is **May 15, 2016**, with decisions announced approximately one month thereafter (depending on confirmation of available funds from different sponsors).

4. Bids to host the 19th ICHA Conference

During 2016, ISSHA members will be asked to vote for which site will host the 19th ICHA (2020) that will follow the 18th ICHA in Nantes, France (2018). The chosen site will be announced during the closing ceremony of the 16th ICHA (Florianópolis, October 2016). Now is the time to ask for bids to host the 19th ICHA, so that voters will have the time to examine the different options and make up their mind. ISSHA members in good standing who cannot attend the Conference will have the opportunity to vote on-line at the ISSHA website. Dead-

line for on-line voting (the only way to do it) will be **October 4, 2016 at noon (12.00) Brazil time**. The elected venue will be announced during the closing ceremony of the 17 ICHA.

Bids should be submitted before 31 July 2016, and should include the following information:

- Scientists and organizations who will serve as local hosts, including evidence of their prior expertise in the organization and financial management of similar-sized international conferences.
- Description of the meeting venue and capacity of meeting space for a 5-day meeting, including a plenary room, 2 rooms for simultaneous sessions and several small rooms for administrative use and other necessities.
- Estimated participation is between 400 and 600 people, but sometimes there are surprises, as it was the case during the 10th ICHA (St Pete Beach, Florida), with around 800 participants.
- Availability of accommodations at a range of costs, including the number of rooms, distance from the meeting location, and room costs for high and low seasons.
- If university residence or other inexpensive accommodation is available for students, this will be considered favourably.
- Distance of meeting and lodging facilities from major airport(s) and cost of transportation between airport and meeting and lodging facilities.
- Availability of local public transportation.
- Expected cost of lunches per day.
- Availability and distance to restaurants for lunches.
- Expected level of local support and associated funding, including ability to provide meeting space, audiovisual support, and staff support, at no cost to the international organizers.
- Dates when the facility would be available in 2020.
- Plans for mid-week excursions and accompanying persons' activities.
- HAB scientists who would be responsible for editing the ICHA proceedings¹, including evidence of their prior experience in producing English language conference proceedings¹.

Enquiries and bids should be e-mailed to the President of ISSHA (*vera.l.trainer@noaa.gov*) c/c to the Chair of the ISSHA Conference Committee (*beatriz.reguera@vi.ieo.es*). Bids should be limited to 2-3 pages, plus supplementary illustrations and web links. Information on the previous ICHA venues can be found at the ISSHA website Conferences. Bids will be examined by the ISSHA Council and posted on the ISSHA website.

1) Nowadays, the edited ICHA proceedings are published on-line on the ICHA website (no hard copies). Traditionally, ICHA proceedings have been edited by a group led by the head of the local organizing committee. If the local hosts are not willing to do it, the ISSHA Committee on Publications and Dissemination will take it over.

5. Donations for the ISSHA Auction 2016

ISSHA auctions during past International Conferences on Harmful Algae have been a success and are now a tradition!! It is an opportunity for the conference participants to bid on donated items. The range of items is broad and may include books, signed reprints, photos, jewellery, T-shirts, paintings, algae-related items, liquor, and scientific equipment. The auction items are donated by ISSHA members from around the world. Funds collected during the auction are an important income for ISSHA. ISSHA was able to offer partial travel support to 30 students to attend the 2014 conference in Wellington.

Please contact the responsible person for the auction, Dr Ester Garcés (*esther@icm.csic.es*) about your donations for the auction and the way you are going to transport it. Please, write "ISSHA Auction 2016" in the message subject. You may also include a picture of your item if you wish. A list of items will be presented on the ISSHA website. An address where items may be sent in advance of the meeting will be provided on the conference website.

6. Nominations for ISSHA Executive and Council (Elections 2016)

The composition of ISSHA Executive and Council following the 2014 elections is as follows:

Executive Officers

- President: Vera TRAINER (USA)
- 1st Vice-President: Gustaaf HALLEGRAEFF (Australia)
- 2nd Vice President: Robin RAINE (Ireland)
- Secretary: Anke KREMP (Finland)
- Treasurer: Henrik ENEVOLDSEN (Denmark)
- Past President: Beatriz REGUERA (Spain)

Council Members

- Ana AMORIN (Portugal)
- Katerina ALIGIZAKI (Greece)
- Ana AMORIN (Portugal)
- Christine BAND-SCHMIDT (Mexico)
- Keith DAVIDSON (United Kingdom)
- Marta ESTRADA (Spain)
- Esther GARCÉS (Spain)
- Anna GODHE (Sweden)
- Ian JENKINSON (China, France)
- Katerine LEBRET (Sweden)
- Lincoln MCKENZIE (New Zealand)
- Luis PROENÇA (Brazil)
- Suzanne ROY (Canada)
- Aurelia TUBARO (Italy)

According to ISSHA's statutes, all the executive officers can be re-elected, after nomination, for another term (2 years) with the exception of Robin Raine, who has already served as Vice-President for two terms.

Nominations are invited for candidates to stand for election/re-election to the Executive Committee (Officers) and the Council of ISSHA. Nominations may be made by any current ISSHA member, including the nominee, and should specify the position concerned (President, Vice-President, Secretary, Treasurer or Ordinary Council Member). Written consent of the prospective candidate should always accompany the nomination. **Nominations from Asia are encouraged, because this part of the world has lots of ISSHA members but is poorly represented in the Council.**

Nominations should be sent to both the president, Vera Trainer (*vera.l.trainer@noaa.gov*) and the secretary Anke Kremp (*anke.kremp@ym-paristo.fi*). The deadline for receipt of nominations is **15 June 2016**. Elections will be held before the General Assembly scheduled for 13 October 2016.

John W. Hurst, Jr. 1927 - 2015

For 53 years, John W. Hurst, Jr. was a fixture at the Maine Department of Marine Resources, and known throughout the world for his contributions to the field of harmful algae. John was born and raised in Bozeman, Montana and after graduating from Montana State University in 1949, he began his life-long career at the Maine Department of Sea and Shore Fisheries (now Department of Marine Resources - DMR) where he developed the monitoring system for PSP. Over the course of his career he was called many things, "Grandfather of Red Tide", "the Czar", and the "Red Tide Guru" among them. But to most who knew him, he was John - a very giving mentor and friend.

John started the Maine Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) monitoring program in 1958 following a serious outbreak of toxicity in neighboring Canada. Over the ensuing 52 years, John continued to develop and perfect that program, and guarded and protected the State of Maine shellfisheries in the face of a highly unpredictable public health issue. It is a testament to his knowledge and perseverance that his program has been held up to the rest of world as the 'gold standard' of monitoring programs.

One cannot think about shellfish safety or red tide anywhere in the world without hearing the name John Hurst. John understood the importance of long-term data sets before it was a 'term' and made his data available to many scientific collaborators over the years - indeed, many of the models being developed today are based on what John knew to be true 40 years ago! Perhaps of even more consequence was his very special ability to engage young kids and fuel their curiosity and enthusiasm.

His office was filled with testaments to his accomplishments. He and his several teams were recognized with the Commissioner's Special Citation from the U.S. Food and Drug Administration and the Governor's Award for Special Teamwork, the Canadian Food Inspection Agency, the Maine legislature, and Governor Angus King. In 2001, John was awarded the Wallace Award from the National Shellfisheries Association, and in 2002 he was presented with a Lifetime Achievement Award for his contributions to research and monitoring of marine biotoxins at the Xth International Conference on Harmful Algae. The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) designated John as a Trailblazer (see <http://www.issaha.org/Welcome-to-ISSHA/HAB-Trail-Blazers/John-Hurst>). All of these recognitions were richly deserved, but John was most proud of the fact that no cases of PSP were ever reported in the State of Maine from commercially harvested

shellfish while he was on the job. He listened to the industry and they listened to him and together they built a stellar monitoring program which was emulated globally. John was a constant source of data and experience and shared his knowledge freely with scientists and managers from all corners of the globe for over five decades.

On a more personal note, John was my introduction to the world of toxic algae in 1982 and we remained friends and colleagues for the decades that followed. He was encouraging early on when I suggested that the toxins might well be affecting the shellfish, always interested in research questions, and always willing to provide support where he could and lively discussions and wisdom on a daily basis to any who asked (and to some who didn't!).

He and his young son Dan (who predeceased him) named their basset hound after me and I always smiled when I saw John walking the legs off that dog on their daily jaunt to town. After I left the DMR, John and I remained colleagues and friends and I always knew where to turn when I needed some common sense advice and information. He's missed.

John is survived by his wife Nancy, sons John and Peter, daughter Lucy, their spouses, three grandchildren, and a global cadre of people who are better for knowing him and for his contributions.

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The 10th International Conference on Toxic Cyanobacteria

Oct. 23-28, 2016
Wuhan, China

The 10th International Conference on Toxic Cyanobacteria (ICTC10), *Cyanobacteria and Cyanotoxins: From Research to Risk Management*, organized by the Institute of Hydrobiology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, will be held in Wuhan, China, on October 23-28, 2016.

Topics of the conference include: (1) Cyanobacterial detection; (2) Cyano-

toxin analysis; (3) Toxicology and toxicity assessment; (4) Cell physiology and molecular biology of cyanobacteria; (5) Secondary metabolites production and functions: biosynthesis, regulation, biological functions; (6) Cyanotoxin compartmentation and persistence; (7) Ecology and cyanobacterial bloom dynamics: environmental controls; (8) In-

teractions between cyanobacteria and other organisms; (9) Risk management of cyanobacterial blooms and cyanotoxins at scales of catchment, in-lake and water treatment; (10) Remote sensing of blooms; (11) The regulatory environment and compliance.

More information in: [HTTP://WWW. ICTC10.ORG](http://www.ictc10.org)

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 54: 21 July 2016

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Lay-out

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